

ISic1550

I.Sicily inscription 1550

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stucco (on tuff)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Μαρία ἦρως

2. ἀγαθά

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284948

EDR 105576

EDCS 41300024

PHI 175615

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 34.0950

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 04.0042

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 20

Gabrics, E. 1929. Stele sepolcrali di Lilibeo a forma di Heroon. *Monumenti Antichi*. 33: 41-60. At 50-53

Bisi, A.M. 1970. Influenze italiote e siceliote sull'arte tardo-punica. Le stele funerarie di Lilibeo. *Archeologia Classica*. 22: 92-130. At 98 no.2

Di Stefano, C.A. 1984. Lilibeo. Testimonianze archeologiche dal IV sec a.C. al V sec. d.C.. Palermo. At 166-169 no.186 fig.90

Vento, M. 2000. Le stele dipinte di Lilibeo. Marsala. At 71-75 tav.28-29, 33-34.

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1550. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4354402>